

LAKBAY-DIWA ✦
Publishing

e-ISSN 3082-4397
p-ISSN 3082-5741

VOLUME I ISSUE VIII

ECHOES

of **EXPRESSION**

A Creative Folio

DECEMBER 2025
MONTHLY ISSUE
NATIONAL

NATIONAL BOOK PUBLISHER IN THE PHILIPPINES
DTI Business Reg. No. 6488937
TIN 492-741-614
lakbaydiwapublishing@gmail.com
Butuan City, Philippines
+639543906965

Echoes of Expression

A Creative Folio

Volume I, Issue VIII (December 2025), National Circulation

ISSN (Online) 3082-4397 ISSN (Print) 3082-5741

Published Online at www.lakbaydiwapublishing.com

Publisher: Lakbay-Diwa Publishing

DTI Business Reg. No. 6488937 / TIN 492-741-614

lakbaydiwapublishing@gmail.com

Butuan City, Philippines

+639543906965

JONALYN L. BOTIL, LPT

MAENGL Student

Baguio Central University

Baguio City, Benguet, CAR, Philippines

DOI 10.5281/zenodo.17952514

Where My Story Meets Theirs: A Mother's Heart in Contemporary Literature

When I enrolled in this subject, I did not realize how meaningful it would become. I expected to read narratives that had little connection to the day-to-day struggles of parenting, employment, and education. Rather than separating me from my own experiences, it has given me a new perspective, allowing me to listen to contemporary voices that speak to my lived reality: the unsaid exhaustion of caregiving, the silent fears that come with responsibility, the need for identity, and the little victories that keep me going. Through these stories, I came to see that literature is a continuous dialogue that reflects the challenges and aspirations of ordinary people like myself rather than a relic from the past.

The dedication to authenticity in modern literature is what gives it its potency. Interactions with this subject and subsequent encounter with theorists such as Terry Eagleton, Linda Hutcheon, and Francois Lyotard support my impression that this literature is characterized by realism, fragmented narratives, and, as Lyotard further adds, "a plurality of viewpoints" that allow authors to explore the unvarnished realities of everyday life. Modern tales illustrate emotional complexity and imperfection, in contrast to classic narratives that occasionally idealize people. They depict people who falter, doubt, mourn, struggle, and persevere. I found myself pausing frequently while reading these stories, particularly when a sentence or scenario reflected feelings I silently harbor as a mother and student. The line separating personal reality from fiction vanished in those moments.

The anecdotes found in *Arteks of Lakandula* struck a deep chord with me. The majority of the stories are about people who struggle to find their identity and honor their roots while forging their own path, which mirrors the issues I deal with. Like them, I have expectations. Some of which are expressed, and many of which are not. Strength does not always shout; sometimes it is peaceful and steady. It urges me to keep going even when life feels unfathomably heavy. This delicate yet tenacious courage served as a reminder. The hidden work, the juggling of responsibilities, and the unwavering belief that every sacrifice creates a brighter future for our children are all reflected in this quiet perseverance.

In many ways, modern literature became a mirror that helped me understand my own sacrifices more deeply. Being a mother while trying to succeed in my career and responsibilities at home requires a kind of strength that often goes unnoticed. This struggle is clearly reflected in Maya, the mother in Lualhati Bautista's *Desire*, who carries the weight of

Echoes of Expression

A Creative Folio

Volume I, Issue VIII (December 2025), National Circulation

ISSN (Online) 3082-4397 ISSN (Print) 3082-5741

Published Online at www.lakbaydiwapublishing.com

Publisher: Lakbay-Diwa Publishing

DTI Business Reg. No. 6488937 / TIN 492-741-614

lakbaydiwapublishing@gmail.com

Butuan City, Philippines

+639543906965

family duties while trying to hold on to her sense of self. Like her, I do my best each day to balance my dreams with my family's needs.

From an academic perspective, this is precisely what makes popular and current literature relevant and essential: it democratizes narrative. It elevates the voices of marginalized populations, women, laborers, young people, and minorities whose stories were previously ignored in traditional literature. Struggles with or issues around gender roles, mental health, poverty, migration, and cultural identity are just a few of the societal realities that these contemporary pieces force readers to face.

By doing so, they foster empathy and deepen our comprehension of the human experience. As I read, I noticed myself becoming gentler and more patient not only with others, but also with myself. This subject gave me a rare chance to reconnect with my own heart. In the daily rush of caring for my family, it is easy to forget that mothers also have feelings, dreams, and fears of their own. Through literature, I found a quiet space where I could slow down, breathe, and listen to the emotions I often set aside. The stories reminded me that I am more than my duties at home. I am a woman still learning, still doubting, and still holding on to my own dreams. Ultimately, Contemporary Literature became a friend during a difficult time in my life rather than just an academic necessity. It made me realize how important it is to share my experience as a mother, student, and woman working to improve. I found strength in other people's voices. I gained empathy from their hardships. I also learnt to cherish my own stories as well as theirs. I knew that I was also a part of the colorful tapestry of modern life living, suffering, developing, and yet learning to create my own story through the interaction between their words and my reality.